

CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS OF GENDER ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH AND HAUSA

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Abstract

This work examines the adjectival formations in gender as obtainable in Hausa and English languages. In order to achieve this, the work analyzed the difference in the morphological processes inherent in the adjectives of Hausa and English in respect of gender. Findings from the study reveal that there are areas of convergence and divergence between the two languages as could be seen in tables 1a 2a 3a 4a and 5a presented in the analysis where the adjectives in Hausa can be inflected or derived by using inflectional morphemes or derivational morphemes to engender the adjectives. The result also shows that both Hausa and English maintain similarity in respect of attributive and predicative positions which indicates that both languages are inflectional languages, morphologically. However, the study also reveals that there are some Hausa adjectives that cannot show gender in isolation except in sentences. On the other hand, the English language does not show such changes at all levels as presented in tables 1b 2b 3b 4b and 5b from the findings of the research.

Keywords: Contrastive analysis, English and Hausa gender adjectives, word formation, affixation

1. Introduction

English language is one of the West Germanic languages which were later separated from its Germanic root due to arrival of the three North Germanic tribes of angles, Saxon and Jutes. Vanderblit et al (1945:23) and Edmond (2007:17) stated that English language is a West Germanic language that originated from the Anglo Friesian dialect brought to Britain by German invaders from various parts of what is now northern Germany and the Netherland.

Hausa language, on the other hand, is of the largest ethnic group in West Africa, according to Robinson et al (2004:141). They are Sahel people chiefly located in Northern Nigeria and Southern Niger. Hausa language is a Chadic language with the largest number of speakers in Africa after Arabic, French, English, Portuguese and, perhaps, Swahili. Predominantly, Hausa communities are scattered throughout West Africa and on the traditional Hajj routine across the Sahara Desert, especially around the town of Agadez. A few Hausa speakers have moved to larger coastal sides in the regions such as Lagos, Accra, Kumasi and Cotonou as well as countries such as Libya. Nowadays, the language is used as a language of trade across much larger countries in West Africa while it remains the lingua franca in Northern Nigeria.

The aim of this study is, therefore, to undertake a contrastive analysis of Hausa and English languages with a view to examining the morphological processes involved in the formation of adjectives of gender in the languages. The main objective is, thus, to highlight the position of genders in a sentence in both languages under study. A cursory look and observation have been made that much studies on gender of English and Hausa have been done but not much in the contrastive morphological study of gender in the adjectives of English and Hausa languages. The research, therefore, intends to view a contrastive morphological study of gender in the adjectives of English and Hausa.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Morphological Process of Affixation

Affixation is one of the morphological processes used to form a word or inflect it. Nnamdi Eruchala (2007:126) asserts that an “Affixation is a method of attaching affixes to the root of words to form new words”. Given the above views, it is trite to say that affixes play a vital role in forming a new word. In both English and Hausa, there are basically two (2) types of affixes. They are; derivational affixes and inflectional affixes. Derivational suffixes are types that their occurrence changes the word

class of the word while inflectional suffixes, when added, give grammatical information in terms of tenses, case and gender. Suffixes are further classified into prefixes (which are added at the beginning of a root word) and suffixes (added at the end of the word). In Hausa, affixation is categorized into three (3) viz; prefixation, infixation and suffixation.

Gender in English

Gender is one of the grammatical aspects in a language even though it differs as languages differ. English makes very few gender distinctions whereby the connection between the biological category 'sex' and the grammatical category 'gender' is very close, Greenburn Sidney *et al* (2000:89). Boeree George (2007:4) also asserts that: “It is called gender because it is loosely tied to the physical sex of people and animals”. Contrastively, gender is not delimited to people and animals. Inanimate objects also do have gender in some languages. Boeree made further discussion on how gender is perceived in some languages by saying that: “Many languages differentiate between masculine nouns and feminine nouns with different ending for each and requiring different articles and adjectives along with them”.

Another view made by Radford (1997:261) on gender goes thus; “Gender is a grammatical property where words are divided into different grammatical classes on the basis of inflectional properties which play roles in processes such as 'agreement' and 'anaphora’”. That is the reason why, while English can use 'small boy' and 'small girl', Hausa uses 'karamin yaro' and 'kamar yariya' respectively for the two phrases. 'Karami' means 'small'. In its masculine form '-n' is inflected in order to make it agree with the masculine noun (head) in a noun phrase. However, -r- is inflected to the root in order to make it agree with the female entity in the noun phrase.

In English, nouns do not have inherent gender properties; so also determiners don't inflect for gender. Only personal pronouns like he/she/it carry gender properties in modern English and these are traditionally said to carry masculine, feminine and neuter gender, respectively. This agrees with how gender is viewed in terms of categorization while some languages consider only three categories of; masculine, feminine and common gender, respectively. In conclusion, gender in English language can be found chiefly and restrictively in nouns and pronouns. For example, 'boy', 'girl', 'man', 'woman', 'she', 'he' etc.

Adjective in English

An adjective in English is one of the primary parts of speech which gives details on a noun or pronoun. Pryse (1984:6) states that; “Adjectives are words which describe noun or pronoun and help us to have a clearer picture of the person or thing they describe or qualify”. In line with the definition provided above, it would be of interest to state that the most universal of the functions of adjectives, which is used as a basis for defining it, is that it modifies a noun attributively and predicatively in English language. For example, “large class” and “the class is large”. In the first noun phrase, the adjective 'large' modifies the noun 'class' attributively while in the second phrase, 'the class is large', the adjective 'large' modifies the noun 'class' but predicatively. Therefore, an adjective could function as part of a constituent attached to the head in a noun phrase.

It is pertinent to state that adjectives in English can only be derived by applying suffixes which in contrast some languages apply different forms of affixes so as to arrive at an adjective of the language. It is trite to note that adjectives in English can also be recognized or identified differently from those endings discussed above. In this regard, Finegan Edward (2008:38) asserts that; "Many adjectives can be recognized by the pattern of their related form, namely: its ending '-er' and '-est' as in large - larger- largest. But those adjectives containing more than two syllables do not permit these endings".

Gender in Hausa

As explained earlier, Hausa, like English, is also characterized by gender. Scholars of Hausa view the concept of gender from diverse perspectives. Galadanci (1973:53), for instance, argues that “Gender can be viewed in two different ways in Hausa: one on the basis of their ending and the other on the basis of the type to which they belong”. He again, distinguishes three (3) categories of gender which include; feminine gender, masculine gender and common gender.

Feminine Gender

Hausa applies suffixes into the noun so as to have feminine or masculine gender. This is the reason why Galadanci (1976:53) maintains that; “Nouns ending with vowels -a/aa are feminine. An example is Mura, Mota, etc... all nouns without exception having any of the following suffixes are feminine: -iya, niya,-uwaa”.

Gender in Hausa is, therefore, identified on the basis of their endings. Examples are; mura, mota, harauniya, hulaliya et cetera. The first two examples end with a/aa while the second two end in the suffixes '-iya' and '-niya' respectively. There are also some group of nouns that are feminine in

which their ending is more or less different from those outlined above. This is why Galadanci (1976:53-4) states that “Proper nouns of female person, names of countries, names of days of the week and some loan words are all classified as feminine”. This agrees with what is obtainable in English in such a way that names of female persons such as; Mary, Aisha, Grace, etc are feminine. In the same vein, names of countries such as; Russia, Nigeria, could be both feminine and neutral because they can be replaced by a pronoun 'she' or 'it'. However, in Hausa, some words such as *lantarki*, *gwamnati*, etc. are feminine gender. By this explanation, it could be argued that the genders are grouped irrespective of their ending but on the basis of their type.

Common Gender

The category of nouns under common gender in Hausa is feminine in as much as the referent is a female. Otherwise it is a masculine gender if they refer to a male person. For instance, '*agola*' '*banza*' '*edita*' '*baini*' '*mage*' etc. Galadanci (1976). This classification can also be found in English in which nouns such as '*doctor*', '*teacher*', '*student*' etc. could either refer to male or female in relation to the context in which they occur. Example in Hausa is; '*Editan ya rasu*' or '*Editan ta rasu*' while in English, thus '*she is an editor*' or '*he is an editor*'. The noun '*editor*' (English) or '*edita*' (Hausa) functioning as feminine and masculine gender in both languages but the only difference is the context it appears.

Masculine Gender

According to Galadanci (1976:55), masculine gender in Hausa has features that are different from those found in feminine gender. For example, '*labule*', '*aboki*', '*bako*' etc are all nouns or masculine gender ending with different vowels apart from *a/aa*. Furthermore, there are masculine genders that end with consonant sounds which cannot be found in the feminine gender. For instance, '*tawul*', etc. This implies that vowels *a/aa* are for the feminine gender, while others like '*e*', '*i*' '*o*' '*u*' and even those that end with consonant sounds are regarded as masculine gender in Hausa. Moreover, just like names of the male person, names of the month of the year discussed under the feminine gender, masculine gender is also characterized by such features irrespective of their endings. Galadanci (1976:55) states that, “Proper nouns of male persons irrespective of their endings are masculine. Examples are: *Bala*. *Audu*, *Wambai* etc. Names of the month of the year are masculine, probably by analogy with '*wata*' (month). Examples: *Jagon wata*, *gambun wata*, *Rajab* etc”.

Adjectives in Hausa

Adjectives in Hausa are of different categories in which Galadanci (1976:30) distinguished unitary adjectives as the key from which the remaining ones were derived. For this, he claimed that “Unitary adjectives can be analyzed in terms of a single stem and a suffix, the suffixes vary according to number and gender”. This implies that in Hausa language, adjectives carry suffixes and these suffixes differ in order to show number and gender. Galadanci (1976:30-1) distinguishes three (3) subdivisions of unitary adjectives on the basis of their syntactic behavior which is parallel by the difference of their internal structure. These are:

Agential Adjectives

This, according to Galadanci, consists of: a stem, an agential prefix 'ma', a suffix '-i' for masculine and 'iya' for feminine”. Accordingly, adjectives in Hausa that carry agential prefix 'ma-' must go along with suffix '-i' or '-iya'. This is to differentiate between masculine and feminine gender. This shows that suffixation is not the only modification that can be used in the formation of Hausa adjectives; prefixation is also included. For example, the noun 'Hakuri' (patience), when the prefix 'ma-' and suffix '-i' or '-iya' are attached to it, will become an adjective in Hausa; that is 'Mahakurci' for masculine gender and 'Mahakurciya' for feminine gender.

Participial Adjective

This consists of a partially reduplicated stem of the structure -acc where 'c' is identified with the final consonant of the stem and suffix '-e' for masculine and 'iya' for feminine. It concurs with a structure of some adjectives in Hausa. For example, the adjectives 'Kamamme' and 'kamanmiya'. The stem is 'kama', where the suffix "-mme' is added to make it a masculine gender adjective derived from 'verb; kama'. On the other hand, in the feminine form 'kamammaiya', the suffix 'mmya' is also attached to the stem to form a feminine gender adjective.

Simple Adjectives

The simple adjectives can be analyzed as consisting of a simple stem and a suffix which varies according to gender and number. This posits that simple adjectives in Hausa are characterized by a simple stem together with a suffix attached to it. For example, 'fari', 'fara', 'baka', 'baki' etc.

3. Theoretical Framework

As pointed out earlier, Hausa adjectives are of numerous categories. This research will, however, settle on the classifications or categories provided by Ahmadu Bello Zaria (1981:17-19) which include:

- a. Adjectives indicating height or length of a person or a thing for example: 'Dogo', 'Doguwa', 'gajere', 'gajeriya' etc.
- b. Adjectives indicating complexion or color of a person or a thing. Examples: 'baki', 'baka', 'kore', 'koriya', 'fari', 'fara', etc.
- c. Adjectives indicating structure of a person or a thing. For example: 'kato', 'katuwa', 'kakkaura', 'kakkauriya', 'guntu', 'guntuwa' etc.
- d. Adjectives indicating conditions of a person or a thing. For example: 'gauro', 'gauruwa', 'makaho', 'makuniya', 'gurgu', 'gurguwa'.
- e. Adjectives indicating state of being of a person or a thing. For example, 'danye', 'danya', 'sabo', 'sabouwa', 'tsoho', 'tsohuwa' etc.

It should be pointed out that Hausa adjectives differentiate between masculine and feminine gender by the use of affixes and partial reduplication in some cases. In contrast, this cannot be found in the adjectives of English accepts adjectives like (tall - taller - tallest) which can be used and this modification is applicable to both genders; it can be 'tall boy' or 'tall girl' respectively.

4. Methodology

In collecting the data for this paper, the study used two sources; primary and secondary sources. The primary source is a collation of sampled adjectives that depict genders in both English and Hausa languages. The secondary source comprises the various literature of the grammars of the two languages where the concepts of adjectives were discussed. These were, thus, used as linguistic models to analyze the sampled gender adjectives collated to determine the similarities and differences in the adjectival formations in the genders of both English and Hausa languages.

5. Data Analysis

This section will provide the analysis of the data collated with a view to comparing the gender adjectives of Hausa and English languages. This would be done using Zaria's classification of adjectives based on; height or length, complexion or color, structure, condition or state of being of a person or an object.

Contrastive analysis of gender in the adjectives indicating color in Hausa and English.

Table 1a Adjectives indicating color in Hausa.

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Bakii	Baka
2	Jaa	Jaa
3	Kooree	Kooriyaa
4	Shuudii	Shuudiyaa

From the data presentation in table 1a, one will realize that, there is morphological alteration in respect of converting an adjective indicating color from masculine gender to feminine gender in Hausa language. This can be appreciated when one analyses that in item one in the table, Bakii (a masculine adjective) changed to 'Bakaa' in order to obtain its feminine adjectival status. While 'Koree', which is a masculine adjective changed to 'Koriyaa' (feminine adjective) and 'shuudii' (a masculine adjective) changed to 'shuudiyaa' which is a feminine adjective. Exceptionally, the adjective 'Jaa' which is a masculine adjective remains unchanged with its feminine adjectives.

Table 1b Adjectives indicating color in English

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Black	Black
2	Red	Red
3	Green	Green
4	Blue	Blue

Contrastively, this is not the same with what is obtainable in English language. 'Bakii' (Hausa) means 'Black' in English. Table 1b indicates that 'Black' which is a masculine adjective is also realized as 'Black' in its feminine adjectival category. Likewise adjectives- 'Red', 'Green' and 'Blue' are in the same category that masculine adjective remain unchanged in feminine adjectives category. For example in 'Bakii' to 'bakaa' the last vowels '-ii' was replaced by affix '-aa' so that to show feminine gender. Likewise in items 3 and 4 in table 1a, the last vowels '-ee' and '-ii' were changed with '-iyaa' and 'yaa', while in the former, its '-ee' was replaced by the affix '-iyaa' so that to show its feminine gender while its latter, '-iyaa' was attached to indicate feminine gender.

Furthermore, the Hausa adjective 'Jaa' which is item 2 in table 1a does not show any morphological metamorphosis in isolation in order to show its feminine gender but this may occur only in the context attributively. For instance, 'Jar mota to zo' and 'jan wando ya bata'. In the two Hausa sentences, the grammatical morphemes '-r' and '-n' were used to show such gender. This indicates that 'motaa' is a feminine noun while 'wando' is in masculine noun. Therefore, it is only in this nature that the adjective 'jaa' can show its gender status.

Contrastive analysis of gender in adjectives in Hausa and English.

Table 2a. Adjectives indicating height in Hausa

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Dogo	Doguwa
2	Matsakaici	Matsakaiciyaa
3	Gajeree	Gajeriya
4	Wadaa	Wadaa

Table 2b. Adjectives indicating height in English

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Tall	Tall
2	Average	Average
3	Short	Short
4	Dwarf	Dwarf

Owing to the data presented in Table 2a. It is right to say that there are morphological changes that occurred in converting an adjective indicating height from the masculine gender to the feminine gender in Hausa. This can be seen when one analyses that in item 1 in the table, 'dogoo' changed to 'doguwa' in order to have its feminine adjectival class. Whereas 'matsakaicii' which is a masculine adjective changed to 'matsakaiciyaa' (feminine adjectives) and 'gajeree' (a masculine adjectives) changed to 'gajeriya' which is a feminine and finally 'wadaa' which is a masculine adjective remains unchanged with its feminine adjectives. Conversely, this cannot be found in English language 'Dogoo' (Hausa) means 'Tall' in English. As for this table 2b indicates that 'tall'(masculine adjective) is also realized as 'tall' in its feminine adjectival status; furthermore, the adjectives: Average, Short, and

Dwarf are in masculine adjectives and they can also be realized as the form in their feminine adjectives category.

Going by the analysis, observation has been made on each of the morphological metamorphosis that occurred in the gender of the Hausa adjectives presented in table 2a revealed that the morphological process use dis affixation which led to the change in the gender status. Therefore, affixes '-uwaa', '-yaa' and 'iyaa' were used. For instance, the adjectives 'dogo' to 'doguwa' the last vowel 'o' was changed with affix '-uwaa' in order to obtain the feminine adjective. This is also happens to the adjectives 'matsakaicii' to 'matsakaiciyaa' the affix '-yaa' was attached to the masculine adjective in order to arrive at its feminine class. Likewise in 'gajeree' to 'gajeriyaa' the last vowel '-ee' in the masculine adjective category was replaced by '-iyaa' which resulted its feminine gender

Exceptionally, the Hausa adjective 'Wadaa' (dwarf) does not change in isolation when indicating gender class but it can show its morphological changes when appears in a sentence. For instance, “wadan mutum ya zo” and “wadar mace ta zo”. Form the given sentences in Hausa, the grammatical morpheme '-n' and '-r' were used to distinguish the gender class. In contrast, English does not show any inflections or affixation in this case, it can only remain the same unless the noun can determine the category of adjective whether it is feminine or masculine.

Table 3a: Adjectives indicating structures in Hausa.

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Katoo	Katuwa
2	Karamii	Karamaa
3	Siiriirii	Siiriyaa
4	Kakkaura	Kakkaura

Table 3a: Adjectives indicating structure in English

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Big	Big
2	Small	Small
3	Thin	Thin
4	Fat	Fat

From the presented data in table 3a, one has to realize that there is morphological metamorphosis in changing or deriving an adjective indicating structure from masculine gender to feminine gender in Hausa. This is can be detected when one analyses that, in item 1 in the table, 'katoo' which is a masculine adjectives changed to 'katuwaa' in order to show its feminine adjectival status. While 'Karamii' which is a masculine adjective changes to 'karamaa' (feminine adjective) and 'siiriirii' (masculine adjective) changed to 'siiriiriyaa' which is a feminine adjective and finally 'kakkaura' which is a masculine adjective remains unchanged with its feminine adjective.

Contrastively, the metamorphosis is not permissible in English language, in table 3b, facts reveal that the adjective 'Big' which is masculine adjectives is al regarded as 'Big' in its feminine adjective category in English, this is also what is obtainable in the adjectives of 'small', 'thin', and 'fat' which resulted no changes in deriving its feminine adjectives class in the language. It is against this background, therefore, observation has been made analytically on each of the morphological metamorphosis that happened in deriving gender of the Hausa adjectives presented in table 3a revealed that the morphological process that is concern in changing the gender from masculine to feminine is affixation. Therefore, the following derivational affixes performed such role of changes: '-uwaa', '-aa' and '-yaa' respectively. For example, in item on the table 3a, 'kaatoo' to 'kaatuwaa' the last vowel 'oo' was changed to '-uwaa' so that to get its feminine adjectival class. Likewise in item 2 in the same table 'karamii' (a masculine adjective) to 'karamaa' where the final '-ii' was replaces by inflectional vowel '-aa' in order to obtain the feminine gender adjective. Furthermore, the adjective 'siiriirii' to 'siiriiriyaa' where the derivational morpheme '-yaa' was attached to the masculine adjective so as to get its feminine gender status. On one hand, the Hausa adjective 'kakkaura' which is a masculine adjective also remain as 'kakkaura' in its feminine adjective; this reveals that the adjective 'kakkaura' does not show any morphological changes when occur in isolation whereas in a context or sentences. For example 'kakkauranmutum ne' and 'kakkaurar mace ce'. Thus the grammatical; morphemes '-n' and '-r' were attached to the adjective so that have gender class.

Table 4a Adjectives indicating condition in Hausa

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Gwauroo	Gwauruwaa
2	Makaahoo	Makauniyaa
3	Gurgu	Gurguwaa
4	Maraayaa	Marainiyaa

Table 4b: Adjectives indicating condition in English

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Divorced	Divorced
2	Blind	Blind
3	Crippled	Crippled
4	Orphan	Orphan

By studying the data presented in the table 4a, one will realize that there is morphological metamorphosis in respect of converting one adjective indicating condition from masculine gender to feminine gender in Hausa language. This can be appreciated when one studies that, in item 1 in the table 'Gwauroo' (a masculine adjective) changed to 'Gwauruwaa' on order too btain its feminine adjectival status. Likewise 'Makaahoo' which has masculine status changed to 'Makauniyaa' so as to obtain its feminine status. More so, 'Gurguu' (a masculine adjective) changed to 'Gurguwaa' as its feminine adjective; and finally the adjective 'Maraayaa' which is a masculine gender adjective transformed to 'Marainiya' as its feminine adjectival category.

Conversely, this metamorphosis does not occur in the English gender adjectives indicating condition, as for this the table 4b reveals that 'divorced' (masculine adjective) is also realized as 'divorced' in its feminine adjectival class. Likewise in the adjectives 'Blind', 'Crippled', and 'Orphan' the operational process is still remain unchanged in the formation of masculine and feminine gender. An analytical observation of each of the morphological metamorphosis that occurred in the gender of the Hausa adjectives presented in table 4a will reveal that, the morphological process that engendered the changes is affixation. Thus it can be stated out in the example analyses. Derivational affixes '-uwaa', '-uniyaa', '-uwaa' and '-iniyaa' were used in the process.

For example, the adjective 'Gwauroo' to 'Gwauruwaa' where '-oo' was replaced by derivational morpheme '-uwaa' in order to have its feminine. So also in 'Makaahoo' to 'Makauniya' the segment '-ahoo' was removed and attached the derivational affixes '-uniyaa' is order to obtain the feminine adjectival status. While in 'Gurguu' (a masculine adjective) to 'Gurguwaa', '-uwaa' in order to have its feminine. So also in 'Makaahoo' to 'Makauniya' the segment '-ahoo' was removed and attached the derivational status. While in 'Gurguu' (a masculine adjective) to 'Gurguwaa', '-uu' was replaced by derivational morpheme '-uwaa' so as to result the feminine adjective. Finally in changing 'Maraanyaa'

to'maraniyaa' the segment '-ayaa' was changed to 'iniyaa' in order to arrive at the feminine adjective class.

Table 5a: Adjectives indicating state of being in Hausa

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Danyee	Danyaa
2	Busasshe	Buusasshiyaa
3	Saaboo	Saabuwaa
4	Matacee	Matacciyaa

Table 5b: Adjectives indicating state of being in English.

S/N	Masculine adjective	Feminine adjective
1	Wet	Wet
2	Dried	Dried
3	New	New
4	Dead	Dead

By looking at the data presented in table 5a, it will reveal that there is morphological changes as a result of converting an adjective indicating state of being of person or thing from masculine gender to feminine gender in Hausa. This can be understood when one analyses that, in item 1 in the table, 'Danyee' (a masculine adjective) changed to 'Danyaa' in order to obtain its feminine adjectival class. As for the items 2 and 4 in the table, 'Basasshee' has become 'Buusasshiya' (feminine adjective), while 'Matacee' which is a masculine adjective has changed to 'Matacciya'(a feminine adjective).

However, this contrary to what is obtainable in English, the adjective does not change when converting masculine to feminine gender. This is the fact that, table 5b, indicates that 'Wet' (masculine adjective) is also realized as 'Wet' in its feminine adjectival category. So also the adjective 'Dried', 'New' and 'Dead' are all masculine adjectives and they remain unchanged with the feminine adjective in the language. An analytical observation of each of the morphological metamorphosis that occurred in the engendering the Hausa adjective presented in table 5a will reveal that, the morphological process that perform the act of engendering the adjectives is affixation. Therefore, it can be seen clearly in the example analyzed. The derivational affixes '-aa', '-iyaa' and '-uwaa' were used. For instance in 'Danyee' to 'Danyaa' the last vowel '-ee'was changed to '-aa' so that to engendered to adjective to feminine

category. Likewise, in 'Busasshee' to 'Busasshiyaa' the morpheme '-ee' was changed to '-iyaa' so that to its feminine adjective and in the case of 'Saaboo' to 'Saabuwa' the affix '-uwa' was used to change the masculine form to feminine adjective. Finally, the adjective 'Matacee' to 'Matacciyaa' the last vowel '-ee' was transformed by the use of derivational affix '-iyaa' so that engendered the adjective from masculine to feminine category.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the researcher is on the view that, adjectives in Hausa can have gender due to the occurrences of morphological metamorphosis but few cases were found in some Hausa adjectives in which they cannot show any changes when they appear in isolation while English adjectives do not permit such changes in all respect regarding the gender. Similarly, gender in the adjectives of both languages under study can function in attributive and predicative positions as pointed earlier in relevant examples metamorphosis occurrences in the language when deriving gender (masculine and feminine) in the adjectives of both languages under review. The

This paper, thus, concludes that morphological metamorphosis can change the Hausa adjectives when trying to get or derive the gender category of Hausa language. Furthermore, the gender in the adjectives of Hausa and English tend to behave similar in terms of order, this means that gender in the adjectives of Hausa come before noun it modifies or after while the gender in the adjectives of English follow suit. It is right to say that both Hausa and English adjectives can function attributively and productivity in the language. Moreover, this paper concludes that English adjectives do not show gender in all respects but Hausa adjectives do, as presented earlier. However, there are certain kinds of adjectives in Hausa that cannot show any differences in terms of gender when they appear in isolation but in a sentence by the use of some grammatical morphemes.

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